

Barriers and enablers of intercropping and enhanced crop diversification in the UK

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Summary

The barriers and enablers of enhanced crop diversification were investigated by LEAF (Linking Environment And Farming) through workshops and case studies undertaken as part of three separate collaborative projects in 2019–2020. The main enablers identified were the perceived benefits of soil health and crop protection. The main barriers highlighted were the cost and availability of suitable machinery for drilling and harvesting, as well as grain separation for certain markets. Increasing the uptake of intercropping and enhanced crop diversification on a larger scale in the UK requires effective knowledge exchange to highlight opportunities and benefits and help overcome practical barriers.

Key words: Intercropping, sustainability, integrated pest management, productivity, integrated farm management, crop diversification, companion crops, cover crops

Introduction

Single variety crop planting approaches have served farmers well over the last 50 years, with the onset of modern technology to complement traditional methods. However, increasingly volatile climate conditions, alongside extreme weather events, have created a growing challenge in pest management and weed infestations (Raseduzzaman, 2016), providing a need to enhance Integrated Pest Management (IPM) and Integrated Farm Management (IFM).

Enhanced crop diversification in the form of intercropping plant species mixtures or ‘plant teams’, companion cropping and extending crop rotations has the potential to improve yield stability (Sukkel & Weih, 2019), reduce pest and disease damage (Mousavi *et al.*, 2011) and build stress resilience in agricultural systems (Yin *et al.*, 2017). There is opportunity for farmers to improve soil structure, enhance biodiversity and conserve water and nutrient resources.

Intercropping entails cultivating two or more crops in a field at once. This can be cash crops, providing a complementary marketable crop or cover crops, contributing to soil regenerative and restorative benefits. Specifically intercropping has gained attention in recent years due to the beneficial effects on soil fertility, nutrient cycling and pest, weed and disease management. Demonstrating intercropping has the potential to increase on farm sustainability whilst still enhancing the environment. (Glaze-Corcoran *et al.*, 2020) However, uptake remains limited to small operations in the UK (Glaze-Corcoran *et al.*, 2020).

Barriers to and opportunities presented by enhanced crop diversification in the UK are illustrated with reference to participant experiences from three knowledge generation and exchange projects that LEAF contributed to in 2019–2020. This paper looks at common themes that arose across

the projects. Case studies identify successes and failures, enablers and barriers, to the adoption of enhanced crop diversification, concluding that a range of approaches will be necessary to support upscaling of these practices in the UK.

Materials and Methods

Through H2020 projects DIVERSify, DiverIMPACTS and Esmee Fairbairn Foundation project SEAMS, LEAF has been working with a range of UK farmers and stakeholders since 2017 on enhanced crop diversification projects. A farmer engagement workshop '*Experiences, barriers and opportunities in plant teams*' was held on-farm in November 2019 at West Gilson Mains, Fife as part of the SEAMS project. The outcome of this event was a summary of plenary discussions between farmers, agronomists and industry representatives. Two farmer led case studies were delivered as part of LEAF's contribution to the H2020 project cluster 'Crop Diversification' which includes the DIVERSify and DiverIMPACTS projects. Enablers of and barriers to the uptake of enhanced crop diversification approaches such as intercropping, companion cropping, and rotation extension were the focus of all three outputs.

Enablers were classified as site-specific farm business approaches which improved access, incentive or motivation to employ enhanced crop diversification strategies. Barriers were categorised as unresolved challenges or perceived risks in the adoption of such approaches.

This study leads on from the research conducted in the DIVERSify project – 'The perceived or realised practical restrictions imposed by plant teams (Pearce *et al.*, 2019)'.

Results

Enablers

Cereals and oil seeds commanded high gross margin for UK arable farms (appendix A) However, short rotations employed to maximise on these margins have led to increased weed, pest and disease burdens (Glaze-Corcoran *et al.*, 2020) and challenges to soil health and nutritional availability (Venter *et al.*, 2016). The primary enablers and opportunities for all farmers involved in the projects focussed on the chance to improve soil health through enhanced crop diversification.

Growing a variety of crops and species benefits the cycling of nutrients by soil biota due to introduction of diverse rhizobial microbiomes and associated microbial specialisms, with a mixture of lateral and fibrous roots adding structural integrity (Saleem *et al.*, 2020), reducing the need for tillage operations to counteract compaction (Büch *et al.*, 2018). The knock-on benefit of increasing deep-burrowing earth worms (*Lumbricus terrestris*) activity, contributing to increased incorporation of organic matter throughout the soil profile (Stroud, 2019). Improving soil health through diversification also was repeatedly observed in the discussions to reduce soil movement and improve drainage.

A secondary enabler was identified in the discussion between farmers and stakeholders as the recognition of systems that lend themselves well to crop mixtures. Mixed farming systems with livestock were found to be well suited to intercropping. For instance, whole-cropped spring barley and peas could be fed back into the farming system as home-grown forage as well as used to build fertility in the rotation through leguminous N fixation. Similarly, where left to mature until combinable the product offered a high protein concentrate feed not requiring mechanical separation. Both of these implementations were valued as acting as a whole farm approach to improve overall productivity, complementing an IFM approach.

However, farms without livestock did not have these on-farm end use opportunities and were reliant on market demand. The success story of one participating farm in the study, farming an all arable system, focused on the trialing of an intercrop of linseed and oats. In the past the linseed crops on

the farm suffered from poor establishment, due to the linseed stems being attacked by Flax Flea Beetle (*Aphthona euphorbiae*) before the seed had chance to emerge. The trial in 2019 investigated whether intercropping with oats would improve establishment of the linseed crop. Linseed and oats were drilled together and once the linseed established the oat companion was then sprayed off. Results showed that pest pressure in the linseed was reduced oats compared to an equivalent linseed crop, negating the need for insecticidal spray. This represents a positive IPM strategy incorporating a cultural method to decrease the reliance on pesticide usage for crop protection.

Barriers

The main barrier identified to intercropping was investment in, and availability of machinery required to tackle the complexity of harvesting two or more crops at once. Crops prone to lodging added to harvesting challenges, as well as the varying moisture levels in the different crop species:

**“Currently in the UK there is no viable off the shelf machinery farmers can purchase to separate seed easily without adding a substantial investment.”
(DiverIMPACTS participant farmer)**

Seed separation and market access was also of concern. Furthermore, there was limited access for mixed crops particularly for human consumption where seeds need to be separated.

One farmer within the study built their own separator to overcome this issue therefore increasing the market access., however this option will not be financially viable for all farmers. Storage was also a factor to consider- growing two separate crops may require more storage, presenting timing issues at harvest for drying and storage space. Other barriers highlighted included establishment and crop management issues, drilling complexity, crop competition and availability of seed. One participating farmer in the SEAMS project was unable to purchase bean seed on the open market in 2019 and was therefore unable to trial the crop mixture on farm.

The final barrier identified was a perceived lack of effective communication between researchers:

**“It’s trial and error.... I still make mistakes.... It’s not a short-term fix”
(DiverIMPACTS participant farmer)**

Farmers were also unwilling to take the associated financial risks without independent and trusted advice, guidance, and training. The DIVERSify, DiverIMPACTS and SEAMS projects have all been working to tackle this knowledge gap, in the form of robust, on farm field scale research trials. The findings of these experiments will continue to be disseminated through knowledge exchange methods including practice abstracts, technical guidance, farm walks, videos, online webinars, podcasts and blogs to showcase and highlight ways to strengthen the benefits and address the barriers.

Discussion

Barriers and enablers have been identified by UK participants in all three projects studies. The cost and availability of machinery acted as the main barrier across the projects. Soil health and fertility was the main perceived benefit of enhanced crop diversification alongside nutrient cycling and IPM. Participating farmers all shared the same positive attitude and willingness to learn, share ideas and experiences and implement enhanced crop diversification on farm.

Enhanced crop diversification has the potential to play a pivotal role for farmers in future by enhancing soil health and fertility and acting as an alternative crop protection strategy as part of an IPM approach, in particular as options of synthetic chemistry become less readily available through legislation and or resistance. Companion, cover and intercropping and extended rotations were all found to have attributes to help solve some of the challenges UK farmers are facing. However, an

increase in effective knowledge exchange to highlight opportunities, with more research, advice and support to help overcome the barriers will be required. Where the balance between the risks of implementation, against the benefit of potential pay offs are addressed, an increase in the adoption of enhanced crop diversification may be seen on UK farms, increasing on-farm sustainability whilst protecting the environment.

As with the majority of on farm decisions there is no single solution and appropriate combinations of supporting management practices are critical. Attention to detail is key, including through efficient use of inputs, market diversification and the adoption of innovations and technology, enacted through a whole farm systems approach such as IFM.

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Appendices

Appendix-A- UK gross margins

(Source: AHDB, 2020 - <https://ahdb.org.uk/news/analyst-insight-wheat-top-of-the-crops-for-2021>).

Gross margins for harvest 2021

	2021/22 yield (t/ha)*	2020/21 Gross margin (£/ha)	2021/22 Gross margin (£/ha)	2021/22 rank	Change
Winter milling wheat	7.92	897	712	1	Unchanged
Winter OSR	3.50	443	652	2	Up 7
Winter feed wheat	7.92	751	646	3	Down 1
Spring malting barley	5.85	540	585	4	Down 1
Winter feed barley	7.08	448	534	5	Up 3
Winter milling oats	6.25	423	526	6	Up 4
Spring feed barley	5.85	457	455	7	Unchanged
Spring milling oats	5.34	339	429	8	Up 3
Winter beans	4.00	512	428	9	Down 5
Spring beans	4.00	507	424	10	Down 5
Blue peas	3.70	483	399	11	Down 5
Spring feed oats	5.34	211	291	12	Unchanged

*Yield based on trend analysis of Defra data where available

Source: AHDB, The Agriculture Budgeting and Costing Book (Andersons)

Appendix B- Case studies

DiverIMPACTS Crop Diversification Success Story: <https://www.diverimpacts.net/success-stories/combined-rotation-cover-crops-and-companion-cropping.html>.

DiverIMPACTS- Case Study 15 Hodmedod's UK (Video):

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CCzC322LaaI>.

DiverIMPACTS Crop Diversification UK Success Story (Video): <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3mkws6luqSY>.

